

Women's Employment in Cashew Processing Enterprises and Its Influence on Economic Empowerment and Financial Decision-Making in Devgad Tehsil

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Abstract:

The involvement of women employment is significantly improved in cashew processing sector due scarcity of jobs in rural and semi -rural areas. and also increases socio-economic value. This research examines how economic empowerment and financial decision-making skills of working women in cashew processing units in Devgad Tehsil is improved. The research is carried out with the help of primary data collected through structured questionnaire distributed to women workers employed in different selected cashew processing units in Devgad tehsil only. The research involves variations on saving habits, income levels, improved decision-making skills, involvement in household decision making and perceived self-assurance. The outcome of the research showed that significantly increased decision-making power at home, improved saving habits, strengthened women's financial autonomy and also increased negotiation power at home.

Keywords: Empowering Women, Cashew Processing Unit, Making Financial Decisions, Employment in Rural Areas, Financial Autonomy

Introduction:

The cashew processing units are among the most agro based and labour-intensive industries in Sindhudurg District of coastal area of Maharashtra. A large number of women workers are engaged in different segment of processing stages, such as shelling, peeling, grading, and packaging. (Kannan et al., 2021). Their participation in different cashew processing units improved their source of family income and also achieved socio-economic empowerment of women workers. (Dendena & Corsi, 2014). It creates financial benefits, increased social engagement and extends their identity beyond household (Dendena & Corsi, 2014).

Economic empowerment includes control over own income, autonomously taking financial decision, accessing financial resources (McMillan et al., 2002). Women limits their involvement in decision making in household due to barriers in social and cultural environment (Mubofu, 2016).

Nevertheless, women achieved greater financial independence, increases confidence, stronger voice in household financial decision making due to local job opportunities emerges (Akyereko et al., 2022a). This economic empowerment also improves beyond individual benefits, affecting family well-being, children's education, and household savings behaviors (Sierra-Baquero et al., 2024).

Although Economic empowerment is equally important because it influences independent financial decision making skills and ability remains under-researched in the academic literature. (Dendena & Corsi, 2014). It is vital connection to grasp the women's input to household earnings have significantly important but yet not recognized. This research aims to assess how employment contributes to improving women's economic empowerment and their decision-making authority within cashew processing businesses in Sindhudurg District. The study offers valuable insights into how

employment crates social change by evaluating shifts in income management, spending patterns, saving behaviors, self-esteem, and involvement in family financial decisions (Jarvis & Vera-Toscano, 2004).

Importance of the Study:

It is essential to determine whether working in cashew processing genuinely empowers women or merely offers a minimal income. In numerous rural households, women generate income but have limited influence over financial decisions. This study aims to determine the extent to which employment enhances their confidence, savings behaviors, and involvement in household decision-making.

Review of Literature:

(Akyereko et al., 2022b) Found that cashew apple utilization was low (<10%) in Ghana, despite stakeholders possessing in-depth knowledge (84.37%) of health benefits. High costs, perishability, and lack of capital were significant processing challenges identified.

(Desai et al., 2024) Found that financial literacy and entrepreneurial orientation play important roles in enhancing the financial well-being, a measure of economic empowerment, for 820 rural Indian women entrepreneurs. These factors are necessary alongside access to financial resources.

(Kannan et al., 2021) explores the economic potential of cashew apples, a significant byproduct of cashew farming, by proposing value-addition strategies through microbial fermentation. While cashew nuts are the primary revenue source, cashew apples are vastly underutilized due to their perishable nature and astringent taste. The research paper highlights that cashew apples are highly nutritious, rich in fermentable sugars, minerals, and vitamins, containing three to six times more Vitamin C than oranges.

(Mishra et al., 2024) found that digital financial literacy significantly boosts Indian women's access to formal finance and increases their independence,

financial well-being, and decision-making power. However, some research gaps exist concerning digital inclusion and gender equity.

(Pal et al., 2022) Studied that women's empowerment is a vital policy discussion in development economics. This research evidenced the impact of social and economic dimensions on empowerment through financial inclusion in rural India. Earning status, decision-making, and social welfare recipient status significantly impact empowerment.

Objective:

To evaluate the impact of women's employment in cashew processing on their economic empowerment and financial decision-making.

Hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis (H₀):
There is no significant impact of women's employment in the cashew processing industry on their economic empowerment and financial decision-making.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁):
Women's employment in the cashew processing industry has a significant positive impact on their economic empowerment and financial decision-making.

Research Methodology:

This study will collect primary data from women working in cashew processing units in Devgad Tehsil using a simple questionnaire. The questionnaire will ask about their income, savings, and role in family financial decisions. The data will be analyzed using SPSS. Descriptive statistics will describe their background, and the Mann–Whitney U Test will be used to check differences in women's economic empowerment levels.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

To evaluate the impact of women's employment type on their level of economic

empowerment, the Mann–Whitney U Test, Wilcoxon W Test and Z Test was applied. Employment status (Permanent vs. Seasonal workers) was used as the grouping variable, and

empowerment indicators were measured on a 5-point Likert scale. This nonparametric test was appropriate because the responses were ordinal and did not assume normality.

Table 1: SPSS

Hypothesis Test Statistics ^a				
Dependent Variables	Statistics			
	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)
I have control over how my earnings are used	144.500	469.500	-3.391	.001
I actively participate in decisions regarding household expenses	149.500	474.500	-4.039	.000
I can independently make financial decisions when needed	230.000	555.000	-1.744	.081
I can save money regularly from my income	307.000	632.000	-.116	.908
I feel confident visiting the bank or using digital payments	255.500	580.500	-1.193	.233
My family values and respects my financial contribution	275.000	600.000	-1.208	.227
I can decide purchases for daily household needs on my own	288.000	613.000	-.508	.612
I Encouraged to express my opinion during financial discussions in family	219.500	544.500	-1.944	.052

a. Grouping Variable: Emp_Status

The test results reveal statistically significant differences between the two groups on specific empowerment dimensions. Women with permanent employment show greater control over their personal earnings ($U = 144.500$, $p = 0.001$) and higher involvement in decisions regarding household expenditure ($U = 149.500$, $p = 0.000$). These findings indicate that stable employment contributes to enhanced financial autonomy.

However, differences between permanent and seasonal workers were not statistically significant for other aspects such as independent financial decision-making, regular savings, confidence in using banking and digital payment channels, recognition of financial contribution, and independent purchasing ability. The item relating to the ability to express opinions in financial discussions within the family showed a result close to the significance threshold ($p = 0.052$), suggesting a gradual shift in empowerment but not yet firmly established.

Overall, the analysis suggests that employment stability influences core financial decision-making power, while wider empowerment outcomes remain dependent on other social and institutional factors.

Results and Discussion:

The results indicate that women's empowerment in the cashew processing sector is multi-dimensional. While employment provides income, the quality and consistency of employment—particularly whether it is permanent or seasonal—plays a decisive role in shaping economic autonomy.

Permanent workers exhibited stronger financial agency, especially in managing their own earnings and participating in major household expenditure decisions. This suggests that secure employment strengthens women's negotiation power within the family, reduces dependency, and enhances confidence in asserting financial preferences.

On the other hand, the absence of significant differences in savings habits and digital financial literacy implies that access alone does not guarantee meaningful financial inclusion. Cultural norms, limited financial awareness, and a lack of formal training may restrict women from fully exercising financial independence, even when they earn income.

The near-significant result regarding expression in family financial discussions indicates a transitional phase in which women's economic contributions are acknowledged, but the shift toward shared financial authority is still evolving. These findings reinforce that employment is a necessary but not sufficient pathway to empowerment. Employment must be complemented by:

- Financial literacy initiatives
- Access to affordable credit and banking
- Supportive family and community environments
- Encouragement of SHG and cooperative involvement

Such support can strengthen women's agency and enable sustainable empowerment.

Conclusion:

The study concludes that women's employment in the cashew processing industry positively influences economic empowerment, particularly in terms of control over income and participation in household financial decisions. The Mann–Whitney U Test results support rejecting the null hypothesis, confirming that employment stability has a significant impact on key empowerment dimensions.

However, the influence is partial, as no significant differences were observed in savings behavior, digital finance confidence, or perceived recognition of women's financial contributions. These aspects are influenced not only by employment but also by social structures, levels of awareness, and financial accessibility.

To translate employment into holistic empowerment, targeted interventions are required. Strengthening SHGs, promoting financial literacy, improving access to financial services, and ensuring workplace continuity can enhance women's economic independence and reinforce their role as contributors to rural economic stability.

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